

INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF PHARMACEUTICAL RESEARCH

FORMULATION AND EVALUATION OF FOOT CREAM FROM *FICUS GLOMERATA* EXTRACT

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ARTICLE INFO

Article history

Received 19/09/2018

Available online
02/10/2018

Keywords

Ficus Glomerata,
Foot Cream,
Moisturizing Agent,
Skin Healing,
Subjective Evaluation.

ABSTRACT

Human feet have to maintain the weight of the body but they are often neglected. The skin on our feet is dry as compared to skin on the rest of the body because it has no oil glands and it relies on hundreds of thousands of sweat glands to keep the feet moisturized, therefore, feet need special care for protection, beautification and comfort. Different types of foot care products available in the market are, viz., Foot powder, Foot spray, Foot Creams, Corn and callus Preparation, etc. Foot cream has the refreshing, anti-pruritic, deodorizing and antiperspirant, cleansing, antiseptic and an antifungal property which prevents foot from the various ailments such as toenail fungus, athlete's foot, bunions, corns, calluses, cracked heels and pressures. Since the times of Vedas different herbs are used to treat various diseases and for treating skin conditions such as eczema, dermatitis, etc. *F. glomerata* is one of the ancient therapeutic herb which has been largely found in India and whole world to treat diseases. β -sitosterol, Gluanol acetate, Dumarin, Lupeol and Lupeol acetate are the active constituents present in *Ficus glomerata*. These active constituents are responsible for the various therapeutic potentials such as anti-inflammatory, antioxidant, antifungal, wound healing, etc. but not much work has been done to evaluate the properties of cosmetic importance. The aim of the present study is to explore the properties of cosmetic values such as skin healing and moisturizing property and on evaluation it was found out that the product gave satisfactory results.

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Please cite this article in press as **Diksha G Ramtekkar et al.** Formulation and Evaluation of Foot Cream from *Ficus glomerata* extract. *Indo American Journal of Pharmaceutical Research*.2018;8(09).

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INTRODUCTIONS

The marked tendency of Cosmetic industries to develop products containing pharmaceutically active principles has led to the introduction of the cosmeceuticals. This term indicates cosmetic-pharmaceutical hybrids aimed at enhancing the beauty of the skin by means of ingredients that modify skin functionally or improve additional health related function or benefit [1-3].

Feet are the important organ of human body and are exposed to a lot of friction and external environment [4]. The lack of oil glands on the sole of the foot predisposes it to dry skin. Negligence towards feet can lead to different disorders generally due to improper footwear, and one can suffer from infection because of the external penetration of the dirt, fungi, bacteria through this cuts and wounds [5]. Neglect of feet may lead to one of the more of the following unpleasant conditions such as penetrating odor of the sweaty feet caused by the bacterial decomposition of the sweat and skin debris, burning and itching sensation between the toes, painful tired and swollen feet; softening of the toenail bed, moist skin irritation, creating ideal conditions for fungal infections. Foot care products have one or more of the following properties such as refreshing, anti-pruritic, callus-softening, deodorizing and antiperspirant, cleansing, moisture absorbing, antiseptic and antifungal [6].

The Indian Materia medica provides clear information on the folklore practices, medicines obtained from wild and traditional aspects of therapeutically important natural products [7]. *Ficus glomerata* is commonly known as udumbar or umber tree. The stem is brown colored and it is reported that stem contains flavanoids, triterpenoids, alkaloids and tannins. The stem is having skin rejuvenating property along with anti tussive, antioxidant, wound healing, antibacterial, antifungal, antifungal and hypoglycemic properties [8, 9]. But not much work has been done till date to evaluate the properties of cosmetic importance.

Present study deals with an attempt to formulate and evaluate foot cream with *Ficus glomerata* extract having moisturizing and wound healing properties which is safe highly stable and gave satisfactory results (fig 1).

PHARMACOGNOSY: *Ficus glomerata*

Scientific classification Kingdom: Plantae (unranked): Angiosperms (unranked): Eudicots (unranked): Rosids Order: Rosales Family: Moraceae Genus: <i>Ficus</i> Species: <i>F. racemosa</i> Binomial name: <i>Ficus racemosa</i> L. Synonyms: <i>Ficus glomerata</i> Roxb[10].

[11]

Fig 1: *Ficus Glomerata* fruit, leaves and stem

Geographical source:

This is commonly found in Australia, Malaysia, Southeast Asia and the Indian subcontinent. It is cultivated all over India and countries near to it [10]. It grows wild in many forests and hills. It is distributed widely from the outer Himalayan ranges, Punjab, Khasia Mountain, Chota Nagpur, Bihar, Orissa, West Bengal, Rajasthan, Deccan, and is common in South India. [12, 13]

Chemical constituents:

Sr no	Parts of plant	Chemical constituents
1	Roots	Euphorbol. Hexacosanoate, tinyatonin, cycloartenol, taraxerone [15]
2	Stems	Taxaxerone, leucoanthocyanins, β -sitosterol, ingenol, stigma sterol, lupeol, Dumarin, ceryl behenate[14], glycosides such as leucocyanidin-3-O- β -D-glucopyranoside, leucopelargonidin-3-O- β -D-glucopyranoside, leucopelargonidin-3-O- β -D-glucopyranoside, and leucopelargonidin-3-O- α -L-rhamnopyranoside; sterols such as β -sitosterol, stigmasterol, α -amyrin acetate, lupeol, and lupeol acetate); and tannins (ellagic acid)[15]
3	Leaves	Racemosic acid, tetraterpene, triterpenoids (basically lanosterol, alkaloids, Gluanol acetate, flavonoids and tannins[15]
4	Fruits	Lupeol acetate, β -sitosterol, glauanol, higher hydrocarbons, glucose, hentrio acontane, tiglic acid, phytosterol, esters of taraxasterol, friedelic acid, glucanol
5	Latex	Euphol, a- amyrin, trimethyl ellagic acid, euphorbinol, isoeuphorbol, tinyatonin, taraxerol, cycloartenol, β -sitosterol, palmitic acid, 4-deoxyphorbol, cycloartenol, and cycloeuphordenol[16]

Applications:

For skin	The stem of <i>audumbar</i> (<i>oudumbar</i>) tree is proved to have healing power [17]. Gives antioxidative and anti-collagenese effect on wrinkled skin and reduce the wrinkled depth [17]. Rejuvenates the skin and make skin soft and supple [18].
For Hair	Leaf juice is massaged on hair to prevent splitting [18]. Extracts are useful in formulation of amazing hair conditioners [18].
Other	It has medicinal value and used for its antidiuretic effect [19]. The roots are well known for its use in the treatment of hydrophobia [19]. Stem possesses very useful properties [19]. The fruits of <i>Ficus glomerata</i> are very effective against leprosy, menorrhagia, leucorrhoea, and blood disorders, burns, intestinal worms, dry cough, and urinary tract infections [19]. Leaf latex is basically used for boils and blisters and measles [19]. It is used as a galactagogue which is helpful in gynecological disorders [19]. Bronchitis, bowel syndrome, and piles can be treated with leaves, in the Unani system of Medicine [20]. The leaf buds are very effective against skin infection [20]. A mixture of leaves powdered along with honey is used in bilious infections [20]. The Decoction of the leaves is used in wound washing and healing [20]. The latex is externally applied on wounds in the treatment to decrease inflammation, pain, and edema, and promote its healing [20]. Latex is also used with sugar to reduce diarrhea and dysentery, especially in children, and improves the sexual power in males [20].

Materials and methods:**Collection of plant material: -**

Stems of the tree were collected from in and around the areas of Nagpur Region in the month of December. These stem were taken to the Botany Department of Rashtrasant Tukdoji Maharaj, Nagpur University, Nagpur for its authentication. The Authentication number of stem is 10154(fig 2).

Fig 2: Authentication of herb.

Preparation of Plant extract:

Collected stems of the plants were washed thoroughly with cold water and were shed dried for 4 weeks. Size reduction was done in electrical grinder (Bajaj GX11) and passed through sieve no 10 μ to get uniform size. About 30g of the powder was taken in the soxhlation with ethanol: water (70:30) as the solvent for about 2 days and 10 complete cycles were performed. After collecting the filtrate, it was distilled to get the water extract (extract coded as *F. glomerata* extract)

Phytochemical investigation:

The extract collected was phyto-chemically investigated for the following Constituents.

1. Test for alkaloids: 5 ml of the extract was added to 2 ml of HCl. To this acidic medium, 1 ml of Dragendroff's reagent was added. An orange or red precipitate produced immediately indicated the presence of alkaloids [21].
2. Test for amino acids: 1 ml of the extract was treated with few drops of Ninhydrin reagent. Appearance of purple color showed the presence of amino acids [21].
3. Test for anthraquinones: 5 ml of the extract solution was hydrolyzed with diluted Conc. H₂SO₄ extracted with benzene. 1 ml of dilute ammonia was added to it. Rose pink coloration suggested the positive response for anthraquinones [21].
4. Test for flavonoids: 1 ml of the extract, a few drops of dilute sodium hydroxide was added. An intense yellow color was produced in the plant extract, which became colorless on addition of a few drops of dilute acid indicated the presence of flavonoids [21].
5. Test for glycosides: The extract was hydrolyzed with HCl for few hours on a water bath. To the hydrolysate, 1ml of pyridine was added and a few drops of sodium nitroprusside solution were added and then it was made alkaline with sodium hydroxide solution. Appearance of pink to red color showed the presence of glycosides [21].
6. Test for saponins: The extract was diluted with 20 ml of distilled water and it was agitated in a graduated cylinder for 15 minutes. The formation of 1cm layer of foam showed the presence of saponins [21].
7. Test for steroids: 1 ml of the extracts was dissolved in 10 ml of chloroform and equal volume of concentrated sulphuric acid was added by sides of the test tube. The upper layer turns red and sulphuric acid layer showed yellow with green fluorescence. This indicated the presence of steroids [21].
8. Test for tannins: 5 ml of the extract and a few drops of 1% lead acetate were added. A yellow precipitate was formed, indicates the presence of tannins [21].
9. Test for triterpenoids: 10 mg of the extract was dissolved in 1 ml of chloroform; 1 ml of acetic anhydride was added following the addition of 2 ml of Conc.H₂SO₄. Formation of reddish violet color indicates the presence of triterpenoids [21] (Table 2).

Preparation of Foot Cream:

Selection of foot cream base:

The base selected for foot cream is Stearic acid and Triethanolamine which forms triethanolamine stearate which acts as a base and gives very light textured cream containing suitable emollients which softens the foot(table 1).

Ideal properties of foot cream :

1. Massage with foot cream should allow relaxation of the feet and hence ready to absorb moisture from the cream.
2. It should soften the cells of the foot.
3. It should stimulate the natural healing process of the skin by hydrating it and regulating the pH balance.
4. The ingredient present in the cream should shield against microbial infections.
5. It should contain the proper dosage of extract in the product.
6. It should stimulate blood circulation, cooling agents as well as providing emolliency and skin softening properties.
7. It should discard all the tensions and treat diseases.
8. It should detoxify feet cells [9].

Procedure:

Following steps were followed for formulating the foot cream:

Step - 1: Preparation of oil phase: the Oil phase ingredients were weighed and heated in the 250 ml borosilicate beaker at the temperature 80⁰ C to form uniform liquid [22].

Step – 2: Preparation of water phase: the water phase ingredients were weighed and heated with continuous stirring in the 250 ml borosilicate beaker at the temperature 80⁰C to form uniform liquid [22].

Step – 3: The Contents of Oil Phase were mixed in the water phases. Three different concentrations such as 1%, 2% and 3% of the total extract of *F. glomerata* extract was added in cream formulation at 35⁰C during the triturating till the uniform dispersion of the ingredient was achieved (Table 1).

Formulations were allowed to equilibrate for 24 hrs, at room temperature and the prepared creams were filled and stored in the air tight glass container. The formulation was further evaluated (fig 3).

Table 1: Composition of Foot cream.

No	Ingredients	Base		F ₁ (%)	F ₂ (%)	F ₃ (%)	Use of ingredients
		F _{b1}	F _{b2}				
1	Stearic acid	10	10	10	10	10	Forms cream base with TEA.
2	Cetyl alcohol	1	1	1	1	1	Act as emollient.
3	Beeswax	2	2	2	2	2	Used as oil phase solvent.
4	Isopropyl myristate	2	2	2	2	2	Good absorption material.
5	Mineral oil	3	5	5	5	5	Gives consistency.
6	Propyl paraben	0.2	0.2	0.2	0.2	0.2	Preservative for oil phase.
7	Triethanolamine(TEA)	0.7	0.7	0.7	0.7	0.7	Forms cream base with acid.
8	PEG-200	5	5	5	5	5	Acts as sec. humectants.
9	Glycerine	5	5	5	5	5	Acts as humectants.
10	Methyl paraben	0.2	0.2	0.2	0.2	0.2	Preservative for water phase.
11	Distilled water	70.9	68.9	67.9	66.9	65.9	Acts as solvent.
12	Active(<i>F. glomerata</i>)	-	-	1	2	3	Has healing and moisturizing property.

Fig 3: Foot cream containing *F. glomerata* extract (3%).

RESULTS:

All the developed formulations were found to be homogeneous, non-greasy, light brown in color with characteristic odor. The studies showed that F₃ formulation complies with requirements of physical parameters and found to be best among all batches.

Evaluation of *F. glomerata* cream:**Physical parameter:**

Color: The formulated cream was tested for color by visual inspection. They were checked against white background.

Odor: The Odor of formulated cream was checked by smelling it.

Consistency: The consistency was checked by applying on skin.

Greasiness: The greasiness was assessed by application on the skin.

Homogeneity: Developed cream was tested for homogeneity by visual inspection. They were checked for their appearance and presence of any aggregates.

Water Wash ability: The formulations were applied on skin; the ease and extent of washing with water were checked manually.

pH determination: Accurately weighed quantity of about 5 ± 0.01 g of the cream was taken in a 100ml beaker. 45ml of water was added and the cream was dispersed in it. The pH was determined at 27°C using the pH meter [23] (Table 3).

Case studies:

From the above observation, it was decided to use cream containing 3% concentration of *F. glomerata* stem extract for subjective evaluation.

Materials and Method: 10 subjects of both sexes, from the age group of 18-65years, who were having symptoms like the hard, dry and flaky cracking of the skin of the heels, and were willing to give informed consent were enrolled in the study. Subjects who were willing to participate in the study were given detailed description about the research product, nature and duration of the study. Also subject's responsibilities after entering the study were explained. The subjects who met the requirements of this section, has signed an informed consent form

Methodology:

The subjects were requested to follow the following procedure for the use of the product for 4 weeks of daily application.

1. Approximately 2 gm of the cream was taken, till the first finger mark.
2. It was gently massaged into the sole of feet in circular motion and cover entire area of foot where dryness was maximum.
3. The subjects were asked to use the cream daily and put the socks for minimum 2 hours for 30 days and note down the changes before and after the use of foot cream.

Follow-up and assessment of subjects were assessed at entry and week 4. Assessment parameters included cracks in heels, dryness of soles, soothing and moisturizing effect. Assessment of parameters was done on the basis of following grading scale: -

Condition of the skin-Cracks in heels:

0: No cracks,

1: Dry soles with one or two cracks.

2: 5-7 cracks,

3: Many superficial cracks

4: Slight deep cracks,

5: Deep cracks with severe pain and bleeding which causes difficulty in walking.

Dryness of sole-

0: No dryness,

1: Slight dryness,

2: Dryness only at the cracks,

3: Dryness over the entire sole.

Soothing and moisturizing effect-

1: No change,

2: Fair,

3: Good,

4: Very good,

5: Excellent.

Appearance:

1: Bad performance

2: fair

3: good

4: very good

5: excellent

Spread-ability:

- 1: Bad performance
- 2: fair
- 3: good
- 4: very good
- 5: excellent

After 4 week, information regarding allergy or any other unwanted conditions were collected from the subjects. All the adverse events reported or observed by subjects were recorded with information about severity, date of onset, duration, and action taken regarding the study of cosmetic. The results were then interpreted in compiled form [24] (Table 4).

RESULT AND DISCUSSION:

Table 2: The analysis of photochemical of *F. glomerata* stem.

No.	Phytochemicals	Inference
1	Alkaloids	-
2	Amino acids	-
3	Antraquinones	-
4	Flavonoids	+
5	Glycosides	+
6	Saponins	-
7	Steroids	+
8	Tannins	+
9	Triterpenoids	+

+ (present), - (absent)

Table 3: Physical parameters of Skin Healing Foot Cream.

No	Physical Parameters	Formulation codes		
		F ₁	F ₂	F ₃
1	Color	white	Cream color	Cream color
2	Odor	characteristics	characteristics	Characteristics
3	Consistency	++	+	+++
4	Homogeneity	+	+	+
5	Greasiness	-	-	-
6	Water wash ability	+	+	+
7	pH	6	5.9	5.6

Consistency: Excellent (+++), good (++) , satisfactory (+)

Homogeneity: homogeneous (+)

Greasiness: non-greasy (-)

Wash ability: washable (+)

Table 4: Subjective evaluation of foot cream with 3% *F. glomerata* extract.

Subject				At entry		Week 4				
No	Sex	Age	Skin type	Condition of feet	Dryness of soles	Healing property	Moisturizing property	Appearance	Spread Ability	Irritancy
1	F	34	Normal	2	1	1	4	4	4	None
2	F	45	Normal	3	1	1	5	5	2	None
3	F	28	Dry	1	2	0	3	4	3	None
4	M	62	Dry	4	2	2	3	3	4	None
5	F	23	Oily	1	1	0	4	5	5	None
6	M	36	Normal	4	3	2	5	3	3	None
7	F	59	Combination	4	1	2	4	4	3	None
8	F	55	Normal	4	2	2	3	4	2	None
9	M	19	Normal	2	1	0	5	5	4	None
10	F	38	Combination	4	1	1	4	5	4	None

Table 5: Demographics details at entry(n=10).

Age Mean±SD(in years)	38.50±16.02
Males:Females	3:7

Table 6: Evaluation of various parameters on the effect on feet.

SR NO	PARAMETER	Score(mean±SD)		Statistical Significance
		At entry	After 4 weeks	
1	Cracks in heels	2.90±1.29	1.00±0.82	p<0.001
2	Dryness of the sole	1.50±0.71	0.6±0.70	p<0.001
3	Moisturizing effect	1.50±0.71	4.00±0.82	p<0.001
4	Appearance	NA	4.20±0.79	NA
5	Spread- ability	NA	3.40±0.97	NA

Note: ^a is significance at week 4 as compared to values at entry.

Fig 4: Statistical representation for subject evaluation of foot cream containing 3% *F. glomerata* extract.

Fig 5: Subjective Evaluation of Subject number 4.

A total 10 subjects were enrolled in the study. The demographic details of the subjects at entry were listed in Table 5. 10 subjects showed reduction in the cracks and dryness, which is summarized in Table 6. The improvement trend was seen from week 1 till the end of the study. There were no significant adverse reactions, either reported or observed, during the entire study period and overall compliance to the treatment was good.

The evaluation of various parameters on the effect of cracks has been shown in table 6. Reduction of cracks in heels at entry was 2.90 ± 1.29 which after treatment with cream reduced to 1.00 ± 0.82 at week 4. Similarly reduction in dryness of soles was noted from 1.50 ± 0.71 at entry to 0.6 ± 0.70 at week 4 with the treatment of Foot cream. Healing and dryness showed a significant improvement at the end of 4 weeks as compared to values at entry. Moisturizing effect also showed improvement from 1.50 ± 0.71 at entry to 4.00 ± 0.82 at week 4.

Statistical analysis conducted has shown that all the parameters had shown beneficial effect on Foot with a significance of $p < 0.001$ as compared to values at entry and week 4 values. There were no adverse effects either observed or reported during study and overall compliance to treatment was found to be good.

The Foot cream which contains *F. glomerata* extract (3%) showed maximum effect on human volunteers. From the results of subject evaluation, it was found that foot cream containing 3% *F. glomerata* extract provide necessary protection and also provides healing property for cracked skin. The results of subjective evaluation showed that the scientific approach applied to formulate herbal foot cream proved to be an effective contribution in the segment of herbal foot cream formulation.

CONCLUSIONS

In the present research work an attempt has been made to formulate herbal foot cream which overcomes the lacunae of available chemical based foot cream formulations. Statistical significant beneficial effect was observed with foot treatment in the parameters like cracked heels, dryness of soles and moisturizing effect. There were no adverse effects either observed or reported during the study. All the subjects completed the study and overall compliance to treatment was found to be good. Formulation F₃ showed the maximum activity. Foot cream was acceptable in view of color, odor, consistency, moisturizing and healing properties and product gave satisfactory results.

F. glomerata stem extract also possesses antioxidant property, therefore, it can be incorporated in skin cream to evaluate its anti-ageing property.

Abbreviations:

<i>Ficus glomerata</i> extract	= <i>F. glomerata</i> extract
F ₁ , F ₂ , F ₃	= Formulation trials with different concentrations of <i>F. glomerata</i> extract.
F _{b1} , F _{b2}	= Formulation trials for Foot cream base.
n	= number of subjects
SD	= Standard Deviation

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

The researchers thank Dr. Deepali Kotwal Madam, Principal of LAD College and Smt. R.P College for women, Nagpur, Dr. Satish Sakharwade Sir, Head- Department of Cosmetic Technology for their constant encouragement and support for the study.

Conflict of Interest:

None.

REFERENCES

- Dange SV, Sudhakar G; Clinical efficacy of foot care cream in the management of foot cracks; IMJ- 2009; 103(10): 350–353.
- Viswanathan V, Kesavan R, Kavitha KV and Kumpatla S; A pilot study on the effects of a polyherbal formulation cream on diabetic foot ulcers; IJMR- 2011; 134(8): 168-173
- Burlando B, Verotta L, Cornara L, Bottini-Massa E; Herbal Principles in Cosmetics: Properties and Mechanism of Actions; CRC press; 2010; 29
- Campion K. ; A Woman's Herbal; 1st ed.; 1988; 88
- Wilkinson J. B., Moore R. J.; Harry's Cosmeticology; 7th ed., George Godwin Publication; 1982; 191-92.
- Anton C. Groot D, Weyland W, Natar JP; Unwanted Effects of Cosmetics and Drugs used in Dermatology; 3rd ed.; Elsevier Publishers; 1994; 558
- Khandelwar K.R.; Practical Pharmacognosy : techniques and experiments; 19th ed.; Nirali Prakshan; 2008; 153-155
- Kirtikar K. R., Basu B. D.; Indian Medicinal Plants; vol 3; 2nd ed.; International Books Distributors; 1981; 2318
- Dr. Singh MP, Panda H; Medicinal herbs with their formulations; vol1; Daya Publishing House, Delhi; 2005; 402-403
- Wikipedia- *Ficus racemosa* : https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Ficus_racemosa
- Ficus Glomerata*: https://www.purdue.edu/hla/sites/famine-foods/famine_food/ficus-glomerata/
- Joy PP, Thomas J, Mathew S, Skaria BP.; Medicinal Plants. Tropical Horticulture. Calcutta: Naya Prakash; 2001; 123-5
- Council of Scientific and Industrial Research; New Delhi, India. The wealth of India- A Dictionary of Indian Raw Material. Publications and Information Directorate; Issue 4; 1956; 35-6.
- Veerapur VP, Prabhakar K. R.; *Ficus racemosa* Stem Bark Extract- A potent antioxidant and a probable natural radioprotector; eCAM 2009; 6(3); 317-324

15. Yadav RK, Nandy BC, Maity S, Sarkar S, Saha S; Phytochemistry, pharmacology, toxicology, and clinical trial of *Ficus racemosa*; PR-2015 Jan-Jun; 9(17): 73–80.
16. Ahmed F, Chandra JN, Manjunath S; Acetylcholine and memory-enhancing activity of *Ficus racemosa* bark; PR-2011; 3:246-9.
17. Paraakh PM; Natural Product Radiance *Ficus racemosa* linn-An overview; 2009; vol 8(1); 84-90
18. Daniel M; Medicinal Plants; Chemistry and Properties; Science Publishers;2006;109
19. Shiksharathi AR, Mittal S; *Ficus racemosa*: Phytochemistry, traditional uses, and pharmacological properties: A review. IJAPR-2011; 4; 6-15.
20. Joseph B, Raj SJ. Phytopharmacological and phytochemical properties of three Ficus species-an overview; IJPBS 2010; 1:246-53.
21. Tiwari P, Kumar B, Kaur M, Kaur G, Kaur H; Phytochemical screening and Extraction: A Review; IPS; Jan-Mar 2011; Vol 1; Issue 1; 103-104
22. Nikitakis J, Lange B; International Cosmetic Ingredient Dictionary and Handbook; Vol1; 16th ed.; Published by Personal Care Products Council;2016;li-lix
23. IS 6608:2004; Indian Standard Skin Creams — Specification; Second Revision; bureau of Indian standards;2004; 3
24. Close B, Coomber R., Hubbard A, Illingworth J; Volunteers in Research and Testing; Taylor & Francis Publishers; 2005; 25, 85; 10.

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